

Book Reviews

Freedom of Enquiry and Expression in the Catholic Church: A Canonico-Theological Study by Jesu Pudumai Doss, SDB. Kristu Jyothi Publications, 2007. pp. xix-398. Rs. 450.

This work of Jesu Pudumai Doss, SDB, is good for any canonical library. The content is timely and practical in the light of some of the current controversies facing the Church. Human rights are those basic entitlements whereby the human person can live in peace, freedom and justice. They are enshrined in international, regional and national instruments, protecting and enhancing the dignity of each human being regardless of their national origin, ethnicity, religion, age, gender, political affiliation, etc. Human rights have deep roots in philosophical discourses, historical precedents, religious thought, and political and social institutions.

This work presents an appreciation and understanding of rights and duties of the faithful in the Catholic Church. In this book the author responds to questions often raised by many: “Do I have freedom of enquiry and expression as a member of the Catholic Church?” and “If I do, what exactly are those rights?” The force behind the book is the current state of affairs of human dignity and freedom of enquiry. The book’s purpose is “to familiarize Catholics with the rights and obligations written into Church law for all its members.”

Chapter one presents a very brief overview of the development of freedom of enquiry and expression in the Catholic Church. The chapter presents rights thinking from the time of Vatican II to the revision and promulgation of the 1983 Code of Canon Law. More could have been included under this particular title, but the reader does indeed obtain an appreciation of the important role of rights in the Catholic tradition.

This chapter concludes by stating that C. 218 of CIC and C.21 of CCEO are the brainchild of Vatican II.

Chapter two is dedicated to the rights and obligations enumerated in the 1983 Code of Canon Law and 1990 Code of Canon for Eastern Churches. In this chapter a detailed account of the subjects, the object and the primary limits of the freedom of enquiry and expression is given. This will certainly aid the reader in a proper understanding of what is expected from the members of the Church regardless of their calling.

Chapter three deals with the complex relationship between the Magisterium and theologians from the beginning of the early Church to our present day.

The final chapter highlights a few aspects of the new horizons that this Canon has opened before the Modern Church. It has focuses on:

a) The new horizons as regards the understanding of the Church and the Christian faithful.

b) Certain implications concerning the dialogue between the Magisterium and theologians

c) and finally, the horizons that enlarge the right-duty to all the faithful.

The reader of this chapter will gain insightful knowledge on the important matter of a right and duty of enquiry of all.

Jesu Doss concludes his work with a series of appendices aimed at furthering a better perception of rights in the Church. This little manuscript will greatly benefit all interested in the promotion and protection of rights in the Catholic Church.

Fr. Roque Alphonso

Classical Indian Philosophy, by Swami Vikrant, S.D.B, Bangalore:
Kristu Jyoti Pbs., 2007, vii + 124. Rs. 60/-

Vikrant intends to introduce the reader to the main ideas of the six classical Hindu *darśanas* and also of Jainism, Buddhism and Cārvāka philosophy. The presentation is reader-friendly. Each chapter is divided into sections and sub-sections, and the headings are in bold. I get the impression that the book is the printed version of the notes he offers to his students.

Vikrant thinks that the “experience of the sacred [by great mystics] seems to be identical, though at the level of articulation there is divergence” (iii). I believe our pre-understanding colours our experience even of the sacred. Hence even the experiences are different. Vikrant also mentions that the history of Indian Philosophy can be divided into three parts, the third “extending, roughly, to the beginning of the eighteenth century” (iv). Have there been no philosophical thinkers in India after that?

The book could have received much more editorial attention. Let me mention some shortcomings. We not only have the initials of Mahadevan, but also a brief note about him (45), but Sheldon is mentioned without even the initials (28), and since there is no bibliography, there is no way of knowing who he is. At times the title carries a Sanskrit word followed by the English equivalent in brackets, while sometimes an English word is followed by the Sanskrit equivalent in brackets (21-22). Given the contents and style of the book, it may not be of much help to the scholar, while a beginner may at times get confused.

Subhash Anand

Global Christianity: Contested Claims, Studies in World Christianity and Interreligious Relations, no. 43, by Frans Wijsen & Robert Schreiter, Amsterdam\New York: Rodopi, 2007, 231.

In this book “scholars of religion and theologians assess the global trends in World Christianity as described in Philip Jenkin’s book [*The New Christendom*, 2002]. It is the outcome of an international conference on Southern Christianity and its relation to Christianity in the North,” held at Radboud University, Nijmegen, Netherlands (4).

Jenkins elaborates some of the claims he makes in his book: during the last fifty years the centre of Christianity has moved towards the South. Within a few decades Christians in Europe and the US will constitute a small fraction of world Christianity. The new churches will not reflect the concerns of the North, “but will seek their own solutions to their particular problems” (15).

W. Ustrof thinks that Jenkins is proposing an alliance between the US leaders and Southern Christianity. This would be disastrous. B. Knighton believes that Southern Christianity is a threat to the US, and that “in the long run Christian faith is propagated not so much by the ‘senders’ in mission, bu the ‘receivers’, or rather the appropriators” (52).

S. Kim and F. Verstraelen criticize Jenkins for basing his conclusions more on statistics, ignoring the quality of life: the impact of Christianity does not depend on numbers but on the integrity of Christians. They base their observations on a study of the Church in Korea, India and Europe. J. Chesworth, studying the situation in Africa, comes to a similar conclusion: “Unless Christians in Africa develop a deeper personal commitment and churches agree to work together, Islam may indeed gain the upper hand in Africa, as they themselves confidently

expect” (129). K. Steenbrink, reflecting on the Christian Diaspora in Asia says: “Christianity will have to come to terms with the remnants of a colonial past and learn how really to behave as a minority religion... It must be a prophetic voice, joining efforts with all positive elements in Asian societies” (134).

Jenkins seems to think that conversion leads to a new affiliation, away from the past. J. Vernooij examines the Church in the Caribbean and concludes that only when there is a good synthesis of the old and the new, will the new remain. H. Gooren reflects on the Pentecostal Churches in Latin America. He finds that conversion need not be lasting. It could respond to a passing crisis and when the crisis is over, the individual may return to his former affiliation.

There are two studies by women theologians. M. Frederiks writes about women in Africa, G. Cruz about Filipina domestic workers in Hongkong. The former group is working with a composite hermeneutic: inculturation and liberation. The Filipinas in Hongkong are discovering the solace religion can provide to people who miss their land and family. Thus these two studies confirm Jenkins thesis that the new churches will seek their own solutions to their particular problems.

Some mistakes escaped the editor’s attention, e.g., “mission would be much more effective is [if?] they were enabled...” (52); “this give [gives?] it a certain affinity...” (56); “The mode and reasons for this growth varies (vary?)...” (70). The book, however, is very neatly done and makes easy reading.

All Third World theologians will find in this volume a confirmation of their basic conviction: only a truly local church can make the Church truly Catholic. All missiologists should make it a point to ready it.

Subhash Anand

A Short History of Christianity in India, By Joseph Thekkedath, SDB., Kristu Jyoti Publications, Bangalore, 2007, x-109.

The book under review is, in the author's own words, a "text book for seminarians, students and young professors." It is a short work of about 100 pages, meant to give a basic knowledge about the origin and development of Christianity in India, but with emphasis on the Catholic Church. It comes from an eminent Church Historian, whose contribution to the study of History of Christianity in India has been immense. He has put together his vast experience as teacher and scholar in these pages and thus has made available to all, especially students of History of Christianity in India, a very short introduction to the History of Christianity in India.

In six chapters supported by maps, a short bibliography of important works on the subject and an index, the book deals with the major topics on the History of Catholic Christianity in India: apostolic origin of Christianity in India, The arrival of western Christianity, the conflict between western and eastern Christianity in India, and the spread of the Catholic Church in various parts of India. The Non-Catholic Churches are dealt with in mere 10 pages. And that remains the main drawback of the book. The title of the book could have been *A Short History of the Catholic Church in India*. A second drawback of the book is that it is a purely chronological account of the spread of Christianity in India whose evident usefulness need not be debated at all. It does give some useful historical information to students of History of Christianity in India and as such will be a help to them.

Isaac Padinjarekuttu

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Kurien Kunnumpuram, SJ

Shake It Off

A parable is told of a farmer who owned an old mule.

The mule fell into the farmer's well. The farmer heard the mule 'braying' -or- whatever mules do when they fall into wells.

After carefully assessing the situation, the farmer sympathized with the mule, but decided that neither the mule nor the well was worth the trouble of saving.

Instead, he called his neighbors together and told them what had happened and enlisted them to help haul dirt to bury the old mule in the well and put him out of his misery. Initially, the old mule was hysterical.

But as the farmer and his neighbors continued shoveling and the dirt hit his back a thought struck him. It suddenly dawned on him that every time a shovel load of dirt landed on his back He should shake it off and step up.

This he did, blow after blow. "Shake it off and step up, shake it off and step up, shake it off and step up," He repeated to encourage himself. No matter how painful the blows, or how distressing the situation seemed the old mule fought panic and just kept right on Shaking it off and stepping up.

It wasn't long before the old mule, battered and exhausted, stepped triumphantly over the wall of that well. What seemed like it would bury him, actually blessed him all because of the manner in which he handled his adversity.

That's life. If we face our problems and respond to them positively, and refuse to give in to panic, bitterness, or self-pity

The adversities that come along to bury us usually have within them the potential to benefit and bless us.

Remember that Forgiveness, Faith, Prayer, Priase and Hope all are excellent ways to Shake it off and step up out of the wells in which we find ourselves.

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